

Distribution, skewness, and homophily: Analysis of global journal-reviewer network

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Abstract

Peer review is vital to the global knowledge production system, and reviewers are the lifeline of peer review. However, little is known about how reviewers of different genders and countries are distributed across journals of various disciplines, countries, and impacts. It is also unexplored whether similar journals will share the same reviewers (homophily) and what journal attributes contribute to that effect. By constructing and analyzing a global journal-reviewer network consisting of 6058 journals and 477684 reviewers from Publons, we show that a small group of journals have disproportionately high numbers of reviewers, degrees, and centralities. Health, Professional fields, and Psychology have more female reviewers. Male reviewers reviewed more journals and more disciplines than female reviewers. The US, China, and the UK are the major countries providing reviewers. Reviewers who exclusively review for a discipline are more diverse than all reviewers in most disciplines. Journals of the same discipline show the effect of homophily of sharing the same reviewers. The results are expected to provide a more comprehensive view of the global journal-reviewer network and facilitate improvement.

Introduction

Peer review is vital to the current knowledge production system and preserves scholarly legitimacy and public trust in science (Johnson et al., 2018; Tennant & Ross-Hellauer, 2020). Publons's survey (2018) suggests that about 13.7 million reviews were undertaken to support 2.9 million publications in 2016. It is deemed as the "least worst" system (Forsberg et al., 2022), and over 98% of researchers in Publons's survey consider peer review extremely important or important to ensure the quality and integrity of scholarly communication (Publons, 2018).

The lifeline of peer review depends on reviewers. Reviewers are the gatekeepers of the article quality, selecting relevant and rigorous articles and reporting irreproducible and fraudulent results (Hojat et al., 2003; Ortega, 2017). Finding good reviewers is a central task for journals to control the quality of their manuscript submissions (Kelly et al., 2014). Ensuring that most journals can access a broad pool of reviewers without inappropriate biases is pivotal to the success of the science enterprise. Knowledge about how reviewers are distributed, connected, and shared by global journals will be conducive to understanding the peer review interactions in global knowledge production.

Previous studies have explored the issues of peer review. Studies found that a few core journals may connect to a large pool of reviewers, while most peripheral journals may have limited reviewers (Lei, 2022). Biases brought by journals can also lead to an unbalanced structure of reviewers, as evidence shows that most active reviewers are male (L. Zhang et al., 2022) and from the United States (Gaston & Smart, 2018), and reviewers in some countries may be more likely to be connected with local journals (Gaston & Smart, 2018; X. Zhang, 2012). Journal editors may invite certain reviewers who are more likely to accept the invitations (García et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2013). It suggested possible homophily among journals with similar characteristics sharing the same reviewers. However, the macro-level journal-reviewer interaction remains unclear due to a lack of investigation of the global journal-reviewer network linked by peer-review relationships.

In this study, we investigate the global journal-reviewer network linked by peer-review relationships. The network is also converted into a co-reviewer journal network, linked by shared reviewers in common. We aim to find out a) how the distribution of reviewers varies across different types of journals and what journals are particularly prominent in occupying reviewer resources; b) whether the reviewers' gender and nationality skew for different types of journals; and c) whether journals with similar features will share common reviewers.

Data and methods

Data

The data used in this study is provided by Publons, a cross-publisher peer-review database now merged into the Web of Science by Clarivate Analytics. We chose Publons because it owns the most extensive coverage of global peer review records and is the most representative so far. According to its claim, until 2018, Publons covers over 15,000 journals, 2.2 million reviews, and 400,000 peer reviewers across a broad range of disciplines and countries (Publons, 2018). The raw dataset contains 1167914 distinct pairs of journal-to-reviewer records, covering 25917 journals and 522589 unique anonymous reviewers. We successfully matched 9220 journals with the Web of Science (WoS) and the Journal Citation Report (JCR) by Clarivate both through machine matching and manual inspection. Furtherly, we removed 3115 journals with less than five reviewers recorded in the dataset to improve its representativeness. Out of the 6105 remaining journals, 6058 journals are included in our analysis for having co-reviewers with other journals, involving 477684 reviewers. Matching with WoS and JCR enables us to collect information about the journal, such as the discipline. We recategorized the journal disciplines into 14 broad disciplines and 144 low-level disciplines used by National Science Foundation for clearer demonstration.

Method

Network analysis

We constructed a co-reviewer journal network based on the multiple-to-multiple relationship between journals and reviewers, i.e., a journal can find multiple reviewers to review manuscripts, and a reviewer can review multiple journals. In the co-reviewer journal network, each node is a unique journal, and each edge connecting two journals represents the reviewers having reviewed both journals (co-reviewers). Edges are weighted by the number of co-reviewers; the more co-reviewers exist, the higher the weight will be for the edge. Corresponding network measures, such as weighted degrees and centrality measures, are computed as descriptive statistics.

Reviewer analysis

Despite the restriction of reviewer anonymity, we requested Publons to infer each reviewer's gender and country using the researcher gender and country classification algorithm developed by Larivière et al. (2013). This approach was originally developed to infer WoS-indexed publications' authors' genders and countries and should not be too biased for reviewers, given that most reviewers are also researchers in academia and authors of academic articles. To ensure accuracy and protect privacy, Publons only returns the inference results agreeing with the reviewers' backend account information. This step allows us to obtain highly accurate gender and country information about the reviewers.

Homophily analysis

We used multiple methods to measure the tendency of homophily in the co-reviewer network. The first is to calculate a journal-level measure, the percentage of intra-group weighted degree,

to examine to which extent a journal's total weighted degree is from edges connected inside the journal's group. If the percentage is high for most journals in a group, these journals will tend to find more common reviewers with same-group journals. The second is the assortivity coefficient. Assortivity coefficient was originally raised by Newman (2003) as a measure of the association intensity between nodes with similar or dissimilar attributes, and Farine has promoted the idea of weighted networks (Farine, 2014). An assortivity coefficient ranges from -1 to 1. A positive value indicates nodes of similar attributes tend to connect to each other, and a negative value means that nodes with different attributes tend to connect to each other.

Results

Centralized co-reviewer network

Using a dataset of 6058 journals from Publons, we constructed a co-reviewer network with 477684 reviewers and 595267 journal relationships. The network is all connected within one community, i.e., no journal is isolated from the major component. The journals have an average of $166.20 \pm (\pm 516.26)$ reviewers, and each reviewer serves for 2.11 (± 2.39) journals in the network. From the perspective of the network, each journal is linked with 196.5 (± 219.8) journals and has 632.9 (± 1700.2) degrees (total number of co-reviewers).

The large variations may result from a small group of journals with disproportionate reviewers, degrees, and centralities. The top 5% (302) of journals with the most reviewers represent 41.9% (421556) of total degrees and are connected with 54.7% (261104) of all reviewers. 21.1% (1279) of journals only have 5~9 reviewers, amounting to 1.3% (6324) of individual reviewers. The three journals with the most reviewers are *IEEE Access* (26278 reviewers), *BMJ Open* (13043 reviewers), and *Scientific Reports* (11006 reviewers). *Scientific Report* appears to be the most crucial journal in the network, with the highest weighted degree centrality, closeness centrality, and betweenness centrality. Other journals ranked high in centrality measures include *PloS One*, *IEEE Access*, *Nature Communication*, and *BMJ Open*. It can be recognized that most of the journals ranked high regarding the centrality measures are "mega-journals," which are usually multi-disciplinary and open-access journals publishing a large number of research articles each year.

Journals by discipline

We classified the 6058 journals into 14 disciplines, 91 countries, and four JIF quartile groups. As shown in Figure. 1, in the co-reviewer network, most nodes in the same discipline appear to cluster together, and there are relatively clear-cut boundaries between disciplines.

Figure 1. (A) Co-reviewer network of journals based on discipline. Journals ranked in the top 10 by degree, closeness, betweenness, and eigenvector centralities are labeled. (B) Lorentz curve of journals and their connected reviewers.

Most journals are in Clinical Medicine (1539), which is 1.85 times the journal number of the second discipline, Engineering and Technology (831). Likewise, Clinical Medicine (155039) and Engineering and Technology (112491) journals have the highest number of total reviewers. These two disciplines also have the highest percentages of exclusive reviewers, who exclusively reviewed for journals in a single discipline. Mathematics (47%) and Physics (47%), on the other hand, are the lowest. Health (64), Social Sciences (57), Psychology (56), and Professional Fields (54.5) have a median of over 50 journals reviewers. The weighted degree distribution also shows a highly skewed pattern. Biomedical Research has the highest average weighted degrees (1013.63), but Physics has the highest median weighted degrees (359).

Figure 2. Journal statistics by discipline. (A) Number of journals. (B) Number of total and discipline-exclusive reviewers.

Skewed reviewers' gender and country distribution

We successfully identified the gender of 203976 (42.7%) reviewers linked in the sample, among which 69.5% (141728) are male, and 30.5% (62248) are female. Female reviewers reviewed an average of 2.33 (± 2.37) journals, and male reviewers reviewed 2.75 (± 3.24) journals. 321 (6.3%) journals in this sample are identified to have no female reviewers, and 4584 (90.5%) journals have lower than 50% of female reviewers.

On average, male reviewers reviewed journals of more disciplines (1.42 vs. 1.37) than female reviewers. Although the percentages of female reviewers in Natural sciences and Engineering-related are as low as below 30%, those percentages in Health, Professional fields, and Psychology are all over 40%. When restricting the reviewers to the exclusive reviewers for each discipline, we found that almost all disciplines see a higher percentage of female reviewers, with Health rising by 9.3% and Psychology rising by 5.7%. It suggests that more female reviewers tend to only review for one discipline's journals, especially for journals in disciplines with relatively more female reviewers.

251806 reviewers' countries are identified. Among all these individual reviewers, the United States shares the highest percentage (41393, 16.4%), followed by China (26636, 10.6%), the United Kingdom (15222, 6%), and Spain (12546, 5%). Germany (3.22 ± 3.98), Australia (3.08 ± 3.35), and Italy (2.98 ± 3.56) reviewers reviewed for the most journals, whereas China (2.08 ± 2.36), India (2.11 ± 2.22), and Brazil (2.12 ± 2.14) reviewers reviewed less.

We calculated the Gini index of the reviewers' countries for each discipline to examine how diverse their countries are. A higher Gini index indicates a greater inequality in the reviewers' country background. Overall, Psychology, Arts, Health, Biomedical Research, and Clinical Medicine have higher Gini indices than other disciplines. The US is the major country for providing reviewers, which for example, accounts for 26.4% of Psychology reviewers and 21.2% of Health reviewers. China provides the most reviewers for Chemistry (15%) and Engineering and Technology (20.86%). For the exclusive reviewers, we found that the Gini indices appear to be lower than all in most disciplines. In contrast, the Gini indices have substantially increased in disciplines such as Arts and Chemistry. It might be related to the large percentage difference of Chinese reviewers in Chemistry, which increases from 15% to 17.1% after restricting to exclusive reviewers.

Figure 3. Reviewers' gender and country. (A) Percentage of female reviewers in all and discipline-exclusive reviewers. (B) Gini indices of reviewers' countries.

Homophily: Do similar journals find the same reviewers?

To have an overview of the homophily, we calculated the percentage of intra-group weighted degree at the journal level and its mean value within groups. Using disciplines as the groups, Clinical Medicine (66%), Engineering and Technology (62.2%), Social Science (61.1%), and Biology (56.5%) journals have relatively higher mean percentages of intra-group weighted degrees. We also use the assortativity coefficient to measure the association between nodes with the same or similar attributes. For the attribute of discipline in the co-reviewer network, the assortativity coefficient is 0.48, implying a relatively high tendency of homophily. The mixing matrix of the weighted edges also shows higher weights in the edges between journals of the

same discipline. The mixing matrices showing the sum of weighted degrees between all two attribute-based node groups also visualized the tendency of homophily. For the discipline, the sums of weighted degrees are larger for nodes with the same disciplines (the diagonal).

Figure 4. Homophily measurement. (A) Mean percentage of within-field degrees. (B) Assortivity and mixing matrix of edge weights among disciplines. Red and green denote that the corresponding edge weights are significantly higher or lower than the baseline.

Discussion and next steps

This study draws on Publons's data of journals and reviewers to investigate the network relationships, particularly focusing on the reviewer distribution and skewness for different types of journals and the journals' homophily in finding reviewers. Given that reviewers are hard to find today (Severin & Chataway, 2021), the unbalanced reviewer pools and connections across journals and disciplines may exert a subtle influence on the standards and quality of peer review and, further, knowledge production and dissemination. The skewed structure of the reviewer population and same-discipline homophily may also bring implicit biases into the peer review process and impede the evaluation of interdisciplinary research.

Next, we will examine the features of the network partitioned by other attributes of journals, such as journals' country and impact, to see whether the conclusions hold. These attributes can be obtained from Clarivate's JCR. We will also use more advanced network analysis methods, such as the exponential random graph model, to examine the tendency of homophily while controlling the covariate effects of node attributes and network structure features. We hope the findings can provide a more comprehensive view of the journal-reviewer network.

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